

Numerical Analysis of an Ejector under Pulsating Inflow Characteristic of RDC Exhaust Conditions

Gregory Uhl^{*}, Said Taïleb[†] and Stéphan Zurbach[‡]
Safran Tech, 78114 Magny-Les-Hameaux, France

Nicolas Odier[§] and Thierry Poinsot[¶]
CERFACS, 31100 Toulouse, France

Marc Bellenoue^{||}
ISAE-ENSMA, 86961 Chasseneuil du Poitou, France

To generate favorable flow characteristics for turbine integration at the outlet of a Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC), installing an ejector or bypass flow device between both components is a viable option. As a first step, an existing ejector is investigated numerically using a Large-Eddy Simulation (LES). Initially, a stationary operating point is investigated and results are compared to available experimental data, where good agreement could be obtained. Subsequently, an axially pulsated flow representative of RDC exhaust velocities is generated at the primary nozzle exit. The amplitude of pressure fluctuations is reduced by about 70% throughout the ejector, whereas the pulsation frequency is retained at the ejector outlet. For the presented operating point, a secondary normal shock appears periodically at the end of the constant-area mixing chamber and retracts upstream as a pressure wave. This flowfield characteristic might not be preferable for a dedicated RDC - ejector configuration due to the introduced net total pressure loss. The shock formation is likely due to the constant-area mixing chamber acting as an aerodynamic convergent under boundary layer presence. This result indicates that an unsteady approach is required to characterise RDC - ejector interaction.

I. Nomenclature

Symbols

A	=	Amplitude
d_{mc}	=	Mixing chamber diameter
d_{ne}	=	Nozzle exit diameter
f	=	Frequency
l	=	Cell size
L	=	Integral length scale
\dot{m}	=	Mass flow rate
P	=	Pressure
\bar{P}	=	Time-averaged pressure
Re_{ne}	=	Reynolds number at nozzle exit
t_c	=	Convective time
T	=	Temperature
U_n	=	Axial velocity
\bar{U}_{ne}	=	Time-averaged nozzle exit velocity

^{*}Doctoral Researcher, Department E&PC.

[†]Research Engineer, Department E&PC.

[‡]Senior Research Engineer, Department E&PC.

[§]Senior Researcher, CFD Group.

[¶]Research Director, CNRS.

^{||}Full Professor, Institut PPRIME, Department FTC.

v_{RMS} = RMS of transverse velocity
 η_k = Kolmogorov length scale
 μ = Entrainment ratio
 ν_{ne} = Kinematic viscosity at nozzle exit

Subscripts

1 = Primary
 2 = Secondary
 4 = Outlet
 s = Static
 t = Total
 w = Wall

II. Introduction

Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC) technologies have received considerable attention in the last decades due to their theoretical efficiency gain compared to conventional constant-pressure combustion systems. In recent years, interest in PGC technologies increased further in light of their potential to reduce emissions when run with hydrogen fuel. A noteworthy example are Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDCs), where one or several detonation waves are circulating continuously around a typically annular, hollow or disk-shaped combustion chamber. Due to the sustained operation in the 1 - 100 kHz range [1], the technology is an attractive option for integration in propulsive and turbomachinery configurations [2–4].

A fundamental difficulty associated with turbomachinery integration is the transonic, highly unsteady, high-temperature combustor exhaust gas that may have a detrimental effect on turbine operation [5]. Klopsch et al. [6] numerically investigated an annular RDC, using a 2D Euler solver. It could be determined that an increasing mass flux increases the outlet Mach number. For the lowest mass flux tested, the outlet was entirely subsonic, with a Mach number fluctuation between 0.25 and 0.9; whereas for the highest mass flux investigated, the outlet Mach was at least sonic. The flow angle oscillated between -20 and 25 deg for the highest mass flux considered; the fluctuation amplitude increased with decreasing mass flux. In another work, Tobias et al. [7] conducted an experimental study of an annular RDC, where an exhaust axial velocity fluctuation between 500 and 1500 m s^{-1} was measured, with an azimuthal velocity fluctuation between -500 and 300 m s^{-1} . It could also be determined that both axial and azimuthal velocity oscillation amplitudes are reduced with a reduced mass flow rate. Naples et al. [8] measured a static pressure oscillation between roughly 0.8 and 1.8 bar in the RDC outlet plane, at a frequency of about 2.9 kHz.

In order to mitigate the detrimental effects associated with combustor-turbine integration, one viable option is to accelerate the RDC exhaust gas into an exclusively supersonic regime, and realize the coupling with a supersonic [9] or a novel bladeless turbine [10]. On the other hand, in order to drive a subsonic turbine, Naples et al. [8] proposed employing an ejector between RDC chamber and turbine in an experimental study. Static pressure fluctuations could be decreased by 60-70% with respect to the RDC exit, which was attributed to both pressure wave expansion and energy transfer to the secondary flow within the ejector. In a follow-up work [4], a classical constant-pressure combustor was compared to the RDC-ejector configuration, using a T63 helicopter engine. It could be determined that the coupling of RDC and ejector had an overall efficiency comparable to a classical constant-pressure combustor for this engine. To ensure operability of the subsonic turbine in a reasonable temperature range, Frolov et al. [11] also mentioned the necessity of an additional component that entrains secondary air, placed between RDC and turbine. Paxson and Dougherty [12] investigated the unsteady behavior of an ejector under fluctuating inflow experimentally, using a pulsejet. It should be noted that the exhaust gas fluctuations generated by the pulsejet were in the low subsonic region, i.e. not representative of an RDC exhaust. Nevertheless, the ejector effectively reduced RMS pressure fluctuations stemming from the unsteady combustion in the pulsejet by an order of magnitude.

The unsteady RDC exhaust gas characteristics point towards an unsteady numerical modeling approach such as Large-Eddy Simulation (LES), to capture the related physics of a mixing component downstream of a RDC. In the present work, the behavior of an ejector exposed to axially pulsating flow is numerically investigated. The amplitude and frequency of the pulsation is of the same order of magnitude than a typical RDC exhaust. The investigation is done in several steps; firstly, an existing experimental ejector configuration [13] at a stationary operating point is modeled

and results are compared to experimental data. Subsequently, the operating point is changed and a sinusoidal acoustic pulsation is added, in an effort to study the unsteady mixing physics within the ejector from an aerodynamic point of view. Temperature, flow angle and species fluctuations typical of an RDC exhaust are neglected in this study.

III. Configuration and Numerical Approach

The computations are done using the compressible, multi-species, massively parallel code AVBP developed at CERFACS [14]. The code solves the filtered Navier-Stokes equations for LES on unstructured grids. A finite element continuous two-step Taylor-Galerkin convective scheme is employed with 3rd order space and time integration [15]. Discontinuities are recovered using the Cook & Cabot model [16]. Subgrid-scale terms are accounted for by the classical Smagorinsky model [17], which has been used in other studies of supersonic shear layers [18]. All walls are modeled using a logarithmic Law-of-the-Wall throughout the entire domain. The studied configuration in this work is the experimentally tested ejector of Kracik and Dvorak [13]. A schematic of the configuration with the main geometric parameters is given in Fig. 1. In this ejector, the primary flow (index 1) is accelerated in a converging-diverging nozzle, mixes with the entrained secondary flow (index 2) in a constant-area mixing chamber, and finally enters a diffuser and constant-area outlet section (index 4). For further details, the reader is referred to the work of Kracik and Dvorak [13].

Fig. 1 Schematic and main geometric parameters of the studied ejector configuration [13].

A. Boundary Conditions and Initialization

Inlet and outlet boundaries are described by Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions (NSCBC). The primary ejector inlet is modeled using the characteristic formalism from Poinot and Lele [19], where axial velocity U_{n1} and static temperature T_{s1} are imposed. At the secondary inlet boundary, total pressure P_{t2} and total temperature T_{t2} are prescribed [20], whereas at the outlet static pressure P_{s4} is enforced [21]. It is worth noting that the sole boundary quantities published for the primary ejector inlet are total pressure P_{t1} and total temperature T_{t2} [13]. However, it was confirmed in the present work that imposing axial velocity U_{n1} and static temperature T_{s1} is equivalent to imposing P_{t1} and T_{t1} (see appendix section). The primary inlet boundary condition is thus switched in preparation for the unsteady inlet case. Nevertheless, in line with experimental data [13], the initialization is done imposing P_{t1} and T_{t1} for both inlets on a coarse computational grid. After obtaining the initial flow field, the solution is interpolated on a finer grid (see section III.B). The boundary values are summarized in Table 1, where index 1 refers to the primary inlet, index 2 to the secondary inlet and index 4 to the outlet (as indicated in Fig. 1).

For the unsteady BC, an existing LES of a RDC chamber has been analyzed as a reference [22]. Instantaneous results in the mean diameter of the RDC outlet section indicated that for the investigated engine and operating point, the velocity magnitude is almost exclusively constituted by the axial velocity. The radial and tangential components did not show a significant influence on the velocity magnitude [22]. Thus, it is a reasonable first assumption to neglect the non-axial components at the RDC outlet, which is done in the present work. Moreover, temperature, species and flow angle variations are not accounted for.

Thus, for the unsteady case, a sinusoidal pulsation of the form $U_{n1} = \bar{U}_{n1} + A_1 \sin(2\pi f_1 t)$ (where \bar{U}_{n1} refers to the mean axial velocity at the primary flow inlet; A_1 and f_1 specify the primary flow inlet velocity fluctuation amplitude and frequency, respectively) is superimposed onto the steady NSCBC inlet boundary condition at the primary inlet, using the formalism from Daviller et al. [23]. The pulsation is imposed as an acoustic forcing. While OP1 is directly inferred from experimental data [13], mean values and fluctuations of axial velocity for the unsteady computation are imposed to ensure a continuous choking and unchoking of the flow at the primary nozzle throat. This generates the typical transonic Mach number range of a RDC exhaust (see section II) at the primary nozzle exit. The operating frequency has the same

Table 1 Boundary values imposed for the stationary ejector computation (operating point OP1)

	OP1	
	Initialization	Simulation
P_{t1}	296.82 kPa	-
T_{t1}	295 K	-
U_{n1}	-	23.64 m s ⁻¹
T_{s1}	-	295 K
P_{t2}	97 kPa	97 kPa
T_{t2}	295 K	295 K
P_{s4}	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa

order of magnitude than a typical RDC exhaust gas. To prevent backflow in the unchoked regime in the secondary channel, the secondary inlet total pressure P_{t2} had to be increased for this operating point. As for the steady case, the flow is initialized on a coarser mesh and subsequently interpolated on the actual grid used in this study (see section III.B). A characteristic boundary condition, where P_{t1} and T_{t1} are imposed, is again used at the primary inlet for the initialization. The second, unsteady operating point (OP2) boundary conditions are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Boundary values imposed for the unsteady ejector computation (operating point OP2)

	OP2	
	Initialization	Simulation
P_{t1}	210.0 kPa	-
T_{t1}	295 K	-
\bar{U}_{n1}	-	23.07 m s ⁻¹
T_{s1}	-	295 K
A_1	-	100 m s ⁻¹
f_1	-	1 kHz
P_{t2}	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa
T_{t2}	295 K	295 K
P_{s4}	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa

B. Grid

The computational grid consists of 51,857,827 tetrahedral cells and 9,111,851 million nodes, which was obtained after a convergence study (see appendix for details). The cell size at the nozzle lip is set to 28 μm , hence, 16 cells are placed on the lip in vertical direction. At the nozzle exit and in the constant-area mixing channel, the cell size is set to 106 μm . In the diffuser and the constant-area outlet section, cell size is gradually increased. Applying the criterion originally proposed by Bellan [24] and also used by Croquer et al. [25] $L/d_{ne} \gg l/d_{ne} \gg \eta_K/d_{ne}$, to the presented cell sizes at the nozzle lip and exit underlines that a reasonable computational grid has been chosen: For supersonic jets, $L/d_{ne} \sim 0.1 - 0.5$ is a reasonable assumption [24], $l/d_{ne} = 0.006 - 0.022$ for the chosen grid sizes, and $\eta_K/d_{ne} = (L/d_{ne})^{0.25} Re_{ne}^{-0.75} = 0.7 - 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$, with a Reynolds number of the jet at the nozzle exit $Re_{ne} = (\bar{U}_{ne} d_{ne}) / \nu_{ne} = 1.68 \times 10^5$ for OP1. The parameters Re_{ne} , d_{ne} , \bar{U}_{ne} and ν_{ne} refer to primary jet nozzle exit conditions (Reynolds number, diameter, axial velocity and kinematic viscosity, respectively); whereas L , l and η_K specify the integral length scale, the cell size and the Kolmogorov length scale, respectively. The dimensionless wall distance y^+ is of the order of 85 in the nozzle region, mixing zone, and diffuser, which is an acceptable value for wall-modeled LES of compressible, transonic flows [26]. The computational grid is presented in Fig. 2 with a zoomed view on the nozzle exit section.

Fig. 2 Fully tetrahedral, unstructured grid for entire ejector (top), with a zoomed view on the nozzle exit section (bottom).

C. Run Details

The steady simulation (OP1) was run for 2 convective times after transitory initialization, whereas the unsteady simulation (OP2) was run for 3 convective times (25 periods). The mean timestep size with the selected grid was 1.8×10^{-8} s, with a Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number set to 0.7. The computations were run on TOPAZE, a French supercomputer supervised by CEA, using 14 AMD nodes, each with 256 GB RAM and 128 cores. The simulation of one convective time required about 28,700 CPU hours, with a wall clock time of roughly 16 hours.

IV. Results and Discussion

A. Stationary Operating Conditions

1. Comparison to Experimental Data

Figure 3 shows time-averaged wall static pressure, normalized with the secondary inlet total pressure P_{t2} , in comparison to experimental and RANS results [13]. The position $x/d_{mc} = 0$, where d_{mc} is the mixing chamber diameter, refers to the start of the constant-area mixing chamber (see Fig. 1). A good agreement between LES and experimental data is found. The increase in wall static pressure starting at roughly $x/d_{mc} = 4$ is due to the supersonic jet breaking up and interacting with the boundary layer, an effect well captured by the LES. This zone also exhibits the highest fluctuations in the domain. A slight overestimation in static pressure is evident for $6 < x/d_{mc} < 12$. Nevertheless, the average relative error, defined as $(P_{s,LES} - P_{s,EXP})/P_{s,EXP}$, could be reduced to 3.3% with the LES (compared to the RANS error of 4.7% [13]). The time-averaged LES entrainment ratio $\mu = \dot{m}_2/\dot{m}_1$ was 0.964, compared to the experimental result of 0.918 (RANS: 1.061) [13]. The sufficient agreement of the numerical results with experimental data confirms the predictive capabilities of the AVBP code for this configuration.

2. Qualitative Flow Description

Figure 4 shows an instantaneous snapshot of a Q-criterion isosurface, colored by vorticity, and plotted over the density gradient magnitude. In addition, the normalized root-mean-square (RMS) transverse velocity, v_{RMS}/\bar{U}_{ne} for several axial planes is shown. The velocity used for normalization, \bar{U}_{ne} , is the time-averaged nozzle exit axial velocity. In vicinity of the primary nozzle exit, i.e. for $x/d_{mc} \leq 1$, transverse velocity fluctuations are small, indicating minimal mixing between primary and secondary flow. Shear layer development at top and bottom secondary flow interfaces is nearly equal, as revealed by the symmetric v_{RMS} profile in Fig. 4b. Primary flow shock diamond structures are clearly visible in this zone (Fig. 4a). For $x/d_{mc} = 2$ and $x/d_{mc} = 3$ (Figs. 4c and 4d), the magnitude of transverse velocity fluctuations increases. Two distinctive peaks are still obvious, although the profile symmetry diminishes. Between $1 < x/d_{mc} \leq 2$, the shock train is minimally perturbed (as revealed by the two shear layers being not entirely parallel to the channel boundary any longer), whereas for $2 < x/d_{mc} \leq 3$, the shock diamonds dissipate and mixing between both flows initiates. For $x/d_{mc} = 4$ (Fig. 4e), the transverse velocity fluctuation amplitude peaks with respect to the other axial stations evaluated. Primary and secondary flow are not distinguishable any longer at this point. Moreover, the influence of the boundary layer is clearly evident for $|y/d_{mc}| \rightarrow 0.5$. For $x/d_{mc} = 6$ and $x/d_{mc} = 8$ (Figs. 4f and 4g), the fluctuations reduce, indicating that mixing is terminating, and a qualitatively mixed turbulent flow is present in the domain at $x/d_{mc} = 8$.

Fig. 3 Time-averaged LES wall static pressure, in comparison to RANS and experimental data [13] for OP1

Fig. 4 (a) Instantaneous isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, plotted over the instantaneous density gradient magnitude, and (b-g) time-averaged profiles of the transverse RMS velocity v_{RMS} , normalized by the time-averaged nozzle exit velocity \bar{U}_{ne}

B. Ejector Behavior under Unsteady Inflow

For the second, unsteady operating point OP2, a sinusoidal acoustic pulsation was imposed at the primary inlet, leading to a periodic pulsation between subsonic and supersonic nozzle exit velocity regime (see section III.A and Table 2). This pulsation is a first step in accounting for the unsteady, high-frequency RDC exhaust. As pointed out earlier, these pulsations do not include temperature, species and flow angle fluctuations for simplicity. In Fig. 5a, primary and secondary mass flow rates are recorded over time at their respective channel exit planes; the resulting local entrainment ratio $\mu = \dot{m}_2/\dot{m}_1$ is depicted in reference to the right ordinate. The abscissa is normalized by the convective time t_c that a hypothetical particle would require to be convected from the primary inlet to the outlet. The imposed frequency of 1 kHz (see Table 2) is well recovered for the primary flow; and mass flow amplitudes of about $\pm 55\%$ from the mean value are visible. The primary pulsation for the chosen operating point OP2 introduces a perturbation on the secondary flow entrainment in the ejector. Compared to the primary mass flow, the pulsation amplitude of the secondary flow is low, thus, the peaks in entrainment ratio are mainly constituted by small primary mass flow rates. The time-averaged

entrainment ratio in this case was $\bar{\mu} = 2.128$, which is roughly 2.2 times larger than for OP1. Compared to classical ejector operating conditions, where $\mu < 1.2 - 1.3$ [27], this value is considerably elevated, a result consistent with several experimental and numerical studies concentrating on RDC - ejector interaction [8, 28]. Figure 5b shows the time-dependent evolution of static pressure at the primary nozzle exit plane and ejector outlet plane. The static pressure signals have been normalized by their respective time-averaged values ($\bar{P}_{s,ne}$ for the nozzle exit, \bar{P}_{s4} for the outlet). The amplitude of the static pressure fluctuations is reduced by a factor of about 70%, whereas the frequency of the pulsation is retained. This result is coherent with experimental measurements in a RDC - ejector configuration [8]. The second peak in static pressure at the nozzle exit (visible e.g. at $t/t_c \approx 2.2, t/t_c \approx 2.235$) is a result of the unsteady shock diamond structure moving periodically through the nozzle exit.

(a) Primary (\dot{m}_1) and secondary mass flow rate (\dot{m}_2), and local entrainment ratio $\mu = \dot{m}_2/\dot{m}_1$ through the primary nozzle exit and secondary channel exit planes (respectively)

(b) Spatially integrated normalized static pressure at the primary nozzle exit plane ($P_s/\bar{P}_{s,ne}$) and at the ejector outlet plane (P_s/\bar{P}_{s4})

Fig. 5 Time-dependent overview of (a) entrainment at channel exits and (b) static pressure fluctuations at the nozzle exit vs. the ejector outlet

Figure 6 shows four snapshots of the instantaneous jet centerline Mach number, static pressure and total pressure between normalized times $t/t_c = 2.927$ and $t/t_c = 3.018$, which corresponds to a single period of the fluctuation. At subsonic velocities in the mixing chamber, the amplitude of primary flow Mach and pressure fluctuations is reduced downstream of the nozzle exit (located slightly before $x/d_{mc} = 0$) due to the absence of a shock train (Figs. 6a and 6b); whereas at supersonic nozzle exit velocities, stronger pressure and Mach fluctuation amplitudes are present (Figs. 6c and 6d). At $t/t_c = 2.927$, the primary flow is choked but becomes subsonic shortly after the nozzle throat, and a completely subsonic flow field ensues downstream of $x/d_{mc} = 0$ (Fig. 6a). In the second half of the mixing chamber at $x/d_{mc} = 10$, however, a subsonic pressure wave is evident that leads to a step-change in Mach number. Shortly after, at $t/t_c = 2.957$, the flow unchokes completely in the primary nozzle, leading to an entirely subsonic domain. The pressure wave observed previously has moved upstream (now located at $x/d_{mc} = 6$), following the reduction in primary inlet pressure. Before entering the nozzle, the pressure wave interacts with the next incoming pulse and is re-injected into the mixing chamber, where it dissipates with the flow. The step-wise drop in Mach number at $x/d_{mc} \approx 5$ in Fig. 6c is the axial end of the Mach stem of the new pulse being injected into the completely subsonic chamber from Fig. 6b. At a time instant later, Fig. 6d, a shock manifests itself at the end of the constant-area mixing chamber at $x/d_{mc} = 12$. The formation of this shock is probably related to the constant-area mixing zone effectively acting as an aerodynamic convergent under boundary layer influence. With the pressure retracting, the shock strength diminishes and eventually, a subsonic pressure wave is formed, completing the observed periodic process. The drop in Mach number visible at $x/d_{mc} = 5$ in Fig. 6d is not a normal shock, but rather related to the locally mixed subsonic - supersonic flow that is

present in the domain at this time instant. Although no detailed pressure loss analysis is conducted in this study, the periodic presence of this secondary shock, transforming into a pressure wave, is considered undesired in RDC-turbine integration due to the danger of obtaining a net total pressure loss.

Fig. 6 Instantaneous P_s , P_t and Mach number along the ejector centerline for four snapshots (a-d) between normalized times $t/t_c = 2.927$ and $t/t_c = 3.018$

Figure 7 depicts four snapshots of an instantaneous isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, over an axial slice of the density gradient magnitude, at the same four different normalized time instants than previously (Figs. 7a to 7d, corresponding to a single period of the fluctuation). The repetitive process of the secondary shock forming, and transforming into a subsonic pressure wave, is clearly corroborated by the gradient magnitude fields. For a subsonic primary nozzle exit flow, few turbulent structures appear for the selected Q-criterion isocontour in Figs. 7a and 7b. Both flows tend to mix rapidly due to the relatively small transverse velocity gradients. Subsequently, the supersonic jet penetrates the subsonic flow in the mixing chamber and shifts the mixing zone downstream (Fig. 7c). At this time instant, the majority of turbulent structures for the selected Q-criterion isosurface are located in the region $x/d_{mc} < 6$, which is consistent with Fig. 6c. At $t/t_c = 3.018$ (Fig. 7d), the supersonic jet is clearly visible, however, turbulent structures are starting to move upstream (towards $x/d_{mc} = 1.8 - 2$) and the supersonic jet will eventually break up, reaching again a flowfield that is equal to Fig. 7a.

Fig. 7 Instantaneous isosurface of the Q-criterion colored by vorticity, plotted over the instantaneous density gradient magnitude for four snapshots (a-d) between normalized times $t/t_c = 2.927$ and $t/t_c = 3.018$

V. Conclusions

A study on the effect of pulsating inflow on an existing ejector configuration has been conducted. Results for a stationary operating point showed good agreement with available experimental data. An axially pulsed flow was imposed at the primary ejector inlet in the second stage of the study. The ejector was capable of reducing roughly 70% of the static pressure fluctuation amplitude. On the other hand, the frequency of the pulsation is retained throughout the device. Additionally, the pulsation peaks lead to the formation of a secondary shock, which moves upstream as a pressure wave due to the rapid decrease in upstream pressure. With the penetration of the next pulse, the process repeats itself. The observed flow field is considered undesired in dedicated ejectors downstream of an RDC due to considerable pressure losses that can be introduced. Moreover, the work also demonstrated that an unsteady numerical approach is needed to capture the unsteady mixing physics within a RDC - ejector configuration. Future work to improve the representation of the RDC exhaust gas characteristics include the implementation of temperature, flow angle and species fluctuations.

Appendix

Impact of Alternative Boundary Condition

This section details the impact of imposing U_{n1} and T_{s1} (BC-UnTs) instead of P_{t1} and T_{t1} (BC-PtTt) at the primary ejector inlet for OP1. No other changes were implemented in the computational setup. The time-averaged results for static pressure and Mach number along the ejector centerline, for both boundary conditions, are presented in Figs. 8a and 8b, respectively. No major differences between both traces are visible. Additionally, axial velocity profiles have been analyzed for both computations in the primary channel inlet plane, where an equally good agreement was obtained. Hence, the impact of the updated boundary condition on the quality of the numerical results is negligible, both globally and locally. The usage of the NSCBC imposing U_{n1} and T_{s1} for the analysis is thus justified.

Grid Convergence

Four fully tetrahedral grids with increasing resolution (12 - 105 million cells, termed 12m, 25m, 52m and 105m) were tested using BC-PtTt (boundary condition introduced in the previous appendix paragraph), see Table 3. The results of the computation were subsequently compared to the results presented by Kracik and Dvorak [13]. In Fig. 9a, the time-averaged LES wall static pressure, normalized with the secondary total pressure P_{t2} , for all four grids is plotted with respect to measurements and RANS results [13]. In Fig. 9b, the respective error bars in relation to experimental data are shown. It is evident that a significant reduction in relative error compared to the RANS result has been obtained. The wall static pressure traces in Fig. 9a agree with experimental measurements for all investigated meshes; and convergence towards a common, small relative error of about 3.3% percent is observed in Fig. 9b. In light of the goals of this work presented in section II, which is to investigate the behavior of an ejector under pulsating inflow, this result is deemed sufficient, and the grid with 51,857,827 million cells (52m) is chosen for the remainder of the study.

Fig. 8 Time-averaged LES results for both steady boundary conditions along the jet centerline for OP1, (a) static pressure, and (b) Mach number

Table 3 Details on computational grids used in the convergence study

Grid Name	Elements	Min. cell size
12m	12,322,319	57 μm
25m	25,298,009	38 μm
52m	51,857,827	28 μm
105m	104,626,867	23 μm

Fig. 9 (a) Time-avg. LES wall static pressure for investigated grids in comparison to experimental data and RANS results [13], and (b) averaged relative error $(P_{s,LES/RANS} - P_{s,Exp})/P_{s,Exp}$ bars with respective standard deviation

Acknowledgments

Gregory Uhl thanks Jan Kracik from the Technical University of Liberec, Czech Republic, for kindly providing the geometry of the investigated supersonic ejector. This work was granted access to the HPC resources of TGCC under the allocation A0122B13460 made by GENCI. The study is financed by the INSPIRE project, Horizon 2020, H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, Number 956803, which is hereby acknowledged.

References

- [1] Rankin, B. A., Hoke, J., and Schauer, F., “Periodic exhaust flow through a converging-diverging nozzle downstream of a rotating detonation engine,” *AIAA SciTech Forum: 52nd AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, National Harbor, Maryland, Jan. 13 - 17, 2014, p. 1015. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2014-1015>.
- [2] Goto, K., Matsuoka, K., Matsuyama, K., Kawasaki, A., Watanabe, H., Itouyama, N., Ishihara, K., Buyakofu, V., Noda, T., Kasahara, J., Matsuo, A., Funaki, I., Nakata, D., Uchiumi, M., Habu, H., Takeuchi, S., Arakawa, S., Masuda, J., Maehara, K., Nakao, T., and Yamada, K., “Space Flight Demonstration of Rotating Detonation Engine Using Sounding Rocket S-520-31,” *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, Vol. 60, No. 1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.A35401>.
- [3] Rhee, H., Ishiyama, C., Higashi, J., Kawasaki, A., Matsuoka, K., Kasahara, J., Matsuo, A., and Funaki, I., “Experimental Study on a Rotating Detonation Turbine Engine with an Axial Turbine,” *26th International Colloquium on the Dynamics of Explosions and Reactive Systems (ICDERS)*, Boston, MA, Jul. 30 - Aug. 4, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [4] Naples, A., Hoke, J., Battelle, R., and Schauer, F., “T63 Turbine Response to Rotating Detonation Combustor Exhaust Flow,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, Vol. 141, No. 021029, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4041135>.
- [5] Asli, M., Cuciumita, C., Stathopoulos, P., and Paschereit, C. O., “Numerical Investigation of a Turbine Guide Vane Exposed to Rotating Detonation Exhaust Flow,” *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2019: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, Phoenix, AZ, Jun. 17-21, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2019-91263>.
- [6] Klopsch, R., Garan, N., Bohon, M., Bach, E., Asli, M., and Stathopoulos, P., “2D Euler Modeling of Rotating Detonation Combustion in Preparation for Turbomachinery Matching,” *AIAA SciTech 2022 Forum*, San Diego, CA & Virtual, Jan. 3-7, 2022, p. 0836. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2022-0836>.
- [7] Tobias, J., Agrawal, A. K., and Paxson, D. E., “Experimental and Computational Analysis of a Rotating Detonation Combustor,” *AIAA SciTech 2022 Forum*, San Diego, CA & Virtual, Jan. 3-7, 2022, p. 1879. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2022-1879>.
- [8] Naples, A., Hoke, J., and Schauer, F., “Rotating detonation engine interaction with an annular ejector,” *AIAA SciTech Forum: 52nd Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, National Harbor, MD, Jan. 13-17, 2014, p. 0287. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2014-0287>.
- [9] Liu, Z., Braun, J., and Paniagua, G., “Characterization of a Supersonic Turbine Downstream of a Rotating Detonation Combustor,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, Vol. 141, No. 3, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4040815>.
- [10] Braun, J., Falempin, F., and Paniagua, G., “Energy analysis of a detonation combustor with a bladeless turbine, a propulsion unit for subsonic to hypersonic flight,” *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 262, 2022, p. 115491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.115491>.
- [11] Frolov, S. M., Dubrovskii, A. V., and Ivanov, V. S., “Three-dimensional numerical simulation of operation process in rotating detonation engine,” *Progress in Propulsion Physics*, Vol. 4, 2013, pp. 467–488. <https://doi.org/10.1051/eucass/201304467>.
- [12] Paxson, D., and Dougherty, K., “Ejector Enhanced Pulsejet Based Pressure Gain Combustors: An Old Idea With a New Twist,” *41st AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference and Exhibit*, Tucson, AZ, Jul. 10-13, 2005. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2005-4216>.
- [13] Kracik, J., and Dvorak, V., “Secondary flow choking in axisymmetric supersonic air ejector with adjustable motive nozzle,” *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol. 204, No. 117936, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2021.117936>.
- [14] Schonfeld, T., and Rudgyard, M., “Steady and unsteady flow simulations using the hybrid flow solver AVBP,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 37, No. 11, 1999, pp. 1378–1385. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.636>.
- [15] Donea, J., Quartapelle, L., and Selmin, V., “An analysis of time discretization in the finite element solution of hyperbolic problems,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 70, No. 2, 1987, pp. 463–499. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(87\)90191-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(87)90191-4).
- [16] Cook, A. W., and Cabot, W. H., “A high-wavenumber viscosity for high-resolution numerical methods,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 195, No. 2, 2004, pp. 594–601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2003.10.012>.

- [17] Smagorinsky, J., “General circulation experiments with the primitive equations: I. The basic experiment,” *Monthly Weather Review*, Vol. 91, No. 3, 1963, pp. 99–164. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1963\)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1963)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2).
- [18] Guo, P., Gao, Z., Wu, Z., Liu, H., Jiang, C., and Lee, C., “Investigations on the accurate prediction of supersonic shear layers for detached eddy simulation,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 89, 2019, pp. 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2019.03.045>.
- [19] Poinso, T., and Lele, S. K., “Boundary conditions for direct simulations of compressible viscous flows,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 101, No. 1, 1992, pp. 104–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(92\)90046-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(92)90046-2).
- [20] Odier, N., Sanjosé, M., Gicquel, L., Poinso, T., Moreau, S., and Duchaine, F., “A characteristic inlet boundary condition for compressible, turbulent, multispecies, turbomachinery flows,” *Computers and Fluids*, Vol. 178, 2019, pp. 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2018.09.014>.
- [21] Granet, V., Vermorel, O., Léonard, T., Gicquel, L., and Poinso, T., “Comparison of nonreflecting outlet boundary conditions for compressible solvers on unstructured grids,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 48, No. 10, 2010, pp. 2348–2364. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J050391>.
- [22] Nassini, P. C., “High-fidelity numerical investigations of a hydrogen rotating detonation combustor,” PhD Thesis, University of Florence, Italy, 2022.
- [23] Daviller, G., Oztarlik, G., and Poinso, T., “A generalized non-reflecting inlet boundary condition for steady and forced compressible flows with injection of vortical and acoustic waves,” *Computers and Fluids*, Vol. 190, 2019, pp. 503–513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2019.06.027>.
- [24] Bellan, J., “Large-Eddy Simulation of Supersonic Round Jets: Effects of Reynolds and Mach Numbers,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 54, No. 5, 2016, pp. 1482–1498. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J054548>.
- [25] Croquer, S., Lamberts, O., Poncet, S., Moreau, S., and Bartosiewicz, Y., “Large Eddy Simulation of a supersonic air ejector,” *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol. 209, 2022, p. 118177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2022.118177>.
- [26] Wang, G., Duchaine, F., Papadogiannis, D., Duran, I., Moreau, S., and Gicquel, L. Y., “An overset grid method for large eddy simulation of turbomachinery stages,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, Vol. 274, 2014, pp. 333–355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2014.06.006>.
- [27] Besagni, G., Cristiani, N., Croci, L., Guédon, G. R., and Inzoli, F., “Computational fluid-dynamics modelling of supersonic ejectors: Screening of modelling approaches, comprehensive validation and assessment of ejector component efficiencies,” *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol. 186, 2021, p. 116431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2020.116431>.
- [28] Paxson, D. E., and Naples, A., “Numerical and Analytical Assessment of a Coupled Rotating Detonation Engine and Turbine Experiment,” *55th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting*, Jan. 9-13, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-1746>.